

ABSTRACT&REFERENCES

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THE THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF THE PREPARATION OF EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT MANAGERS TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF THE SOCIAL COHESION

p. 4-8

Valentina Yastrebova, PhD, Professor, Department of Management of Education and Psychology, Municipal Institution «Zaporizhzhya Institute of Postgraduate Pedagogical Education and Psychology» of the Zaporizhzhya Regional Council, Nezalezhnoi Ukrainy str., 57-A, Zaporozhye, Ukraine, 69035

E-mail: prorektornmr@gmail.com

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-6253-6746>

Tetyana Babko, PhD, Associate Professor, Department of Management of Education and Psychology, Municipal Institution «Zaporizhzhya Institute of Postgraduate Pedagogical Education and Psychology» of the Zaporizhzhya Regional Council, Nezalezhnoi Ukrainy str., 57-A, Zaporozhye, Ukraine, 69035

E-mail: tet.babko@ukr.net

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1066-7290>

The article covers the theoretical and practical aspects of the training of managers of educational institutions for the implementation of the concept of social cohesion in the social and cultural environment.

The urgency of the research is that the formation of civil society in Ukraine predetermines the joint activity of the institution of education with the community in order to solve social problems and enrich the social and cultural environment, but the modern education managers, not having enough activity's experience in the new social and economic conditions, need mastering of the effective mechanisms of the implementation of social partnership with representatives of the environment (state and commercial institutions and institutions, as well as public associations and communities).

The article presents the training program «The Development of the social cohesion of subjects of the educational process» (24 academic hours) developed at the Department of Education of Management and Psychology of the Zaporizhzhya Regional Institute of Postgraduate Pedagogical Education, which was approved during the inter-course training of the heads of educational institutions of the Zaporizhzhya region. This curriculum can be used for the preparation and improvement of the skills of managers of the institutions of higher and postgraduate education.

The authors of the study prove that the involvement of educational institutions leaders in active education and intensive communication in the format of the training contributes to the creation of a new managerial experience of modern education managers.

The article notes that the use of the leaders of educational institutions in relations with social partners of social techniques and methods of interaction will promote the achievement of social cohesion in the social and cultural environment of educational institutions

Keywords: social cohesion, social partnership, heads of educational establishments, training, methods of interaction

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level of professional competence for successful introduction into practice of various innovations, realization in the conditions of inclusion of the tasks. Specialist should have knowledge about the features of organization and work in inclusive education; he/she can creatively apply knowledge in organizing the interaction of all participants in educational and correctional work; to create a development environment in an inclusive educational institution, etc.

The authors highlighted the criterion of the gnostic-technological competence of future speech therapists to work in an inclusive educational institution and indicators for it: the meaningfulness of theoretical and technological knowledge about the features of the organization and work in inclusive education; creativity of technological knowledge and creative approach in organizing the interaction of all participants in educational and remedial work; creating a developing environment in an inclusive educational institution. We have distinguished the gnostic-deontological criterion, because the speech therapist should take into account the management, regulation of various mental conditions of the child with peculiarities of psychophysical development, correction of its defects in the interaction of “special pedagogue - child”. Interaction with the child should not complicate his/her cognitive and educational activities with inclusive education. The child's health status depends on the educational and emotional load.

To carry out the experimental work, we have developed experimental tasks for selected criteria indicators in order to ascertain the level of formation of the gnostic-technological competence of future special teachers to work in inclusive educational institutions. For each task, a rating scale is formed.

Keywords: *inclusion, inclusive education, inclusive environment, gnostic technological competence, developing environment*

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LEVELS OF FORMATION OF GNOSTIC-TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SPEECH THERAPIST TO WORK IN THE CONDITIONS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

p. 9-12

Mariya Berehova, Lecturer, Department of Special Education, Mykolaiv V. O. Sukhomlynskyi National University, Nikolska str., 24, Mykolayiv, Ukraine, 54030
E-mail: beregova3103@gmail.com
ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-4784-4465>

We described the levels of formation of the gnostic-technological competence of future special teachers to work in inclusive education, using the method of questioning and analysis. A special educator must have the necessary

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THE COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF WORLD LITERATURE FICTIONAL ANALYSIS OF THE STUDENT-PHILOLOGIST

p. 13-17

Natalia Hrytsak, PhD, Department of Methodology of World Literature Education, National Pedagogical Dragomanov University, Pyrohova str., 9, Kyiv, Ukraine, 01601
E-mail: grycak78@ukr.net

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-4744-7072>

The article deals with the problem of the formation of would-be teacher's world literature competences that are tightly connected with expert skills and knowledge in foreign fictional work analysis. The methodological heritage on the problem of the formation and development of pupils' abilities and skills in analyzing world literature works is studied. The traditional and newest ways of the fictional work analysis are defined. It has been demonstrated that dialogical reading of foreign fictional work is productive in the formation and development of professional skills and knowledge of students-philologists' world literature fictional analysis. We highlight the basic, intermediate and advanced levels in forming the would-be teacher's world

literature competences. The effectiveness of the professional competence development depends on the methods and the ways of the foreign fictional work analysis chosen by a teacher. We offer the tentative system of tasks that promotes the development of students-philologists' skills and knowledge in interpreting literary phenomena independently, the ability to combine historical, national identity and everyday life, cultural contexts during the analysis of fictional works, the ability to explore plot-compositional, subject-thematic, artistic-aesthetic, linguistic-stylistic levels of fictional work. We focus on students' intellectual and emotional perception of the foreign fictional work that makes it possible to realize the value of fiction, and comprehend the essence of the work, form a holistic view of fiction. It has been demonstrated that the model of analysis of world literature fictional work is directed at a clear, graded, algorithmic sequence of students' learning activities

Keywords: *personality, dialogue, dialogical reading, student, educational activity, types of assignments, text*

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THE PHENOMENON OF THE SELF-EFFICACY OF THE MODERN TEACHER IN THE LIGHT OF THE SYNERGY THEORY

p. 17-21

Irina Makarenko, PhD, Associate Professor, Department of Pedagogy, Kryvyi Rih State Pedagogical University, Gagarina ave., 54, Kryvyi Rih, Ukraine, 50086

E-mail: i.makarenko@ukr.net

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9190-2549>

The article focuses on the importance of reorienting own professional activities of the teacher in the direction of the priority of mechanisms of self-realization, self-development, self-regulation, necessary for his/her professional and personal self-improvement. The importance of the development of the phenomenon of self-efficacy of the teacher as the basis for the disclosure of his/her own potential, aimed at a spiritual activity and obtaining an effective result in professional activity, as well as an important tool for the modernization of the domestic educational space, is emphasized. The essence of the concepts of “self-efficacy”, “pedagogical self-efficacy” is singled out and analyzed. Thus, it is noted that self-efficacy should be characterized by such features as reflexivity and awareness; effectiveness and focus on success; manageability and sequence; ability to self-assess; mobility, flexibility and predictability, etc. The mechanism of development of self-efficacy of a teacher is considered from positions of the synergetic approach, taking into

account the main principles of the synergetic paradigm in education. The attention is focused on the possibilities of synergy for the teaching science in the aspect of consideration of open systems (teacher, teaching staff, the pedagogical system in general), capable of self-organization. It is stated that any teacher in synergy can find the semantic keys for building own trajectory of self-efficacy development management. The teacher should be considered as a productive entity of his/her own professional activities. The essential features of a self-efficient teacher as a synergetic system are described. It is concluded that the most effective teacher in the theory of synergy appears as an active subject of professional activity and agent of changes in the course of the reformation of an educational institution, and expediency of development of the following signs and properties is proved, such as: positive perception of reality; acceptance of oneself, others and the surrounding world in general as they are and what they can be in the future; the ability to set goals, to overcome professional and life difficulties with the installation of self-change; manifestation of existential spontaneity, directness in solving pedagogical problems; confidence in their own professional and spiritual potential as an internal resource of self-development and self-motivation; the ability to really and adequately assess oneself, the vision of both their own positive qualities and disadvantages, etc.

Keywords: self-efficacy, synergetics, professional-personal self-perfection, self-development, pedagogical self-efficacy, critical thinking

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INTEGRATED COMPETENCE OF TEACHING AND ACADEMIC STAFF FOR THE SYSTEM OF POSTGRADUATE PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

p. 22-29

Svitlana Tolochko, PhD, Department of Management of Vocational Education, National Aviation University, Kosmonavta Komarova ave., 1, Kyiv, Ukraine, 03058

E-mail: svitlana-tsv@ukr.net

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9262-2311>

This article analyzes the current normative and legal documents in the field of education, which define and describe the competence of teaching and academic staff of the system of postgraduate pedagogical education, namely: the Law of Ukraine «On Education», the National Qualifications Framework, the Approximate curriculum for training of trainers for educating teachers who will teach first-year students in 2018/2019 and 2019/2020 academic years, Typical educational program of organization and improvement of teaching staff's professional skills by Postgraduate Pedagogical Educational Institutions, Regulations on advanced studying and internship work of academic staff of Higher Educational Institutions. Theoretical and methodological substantiation of the components of integral competence of teaching and academic staff for the system of postgraduate pedagogical education is made: general (capable of transferring from

one subject field to another) and professional (applied in a certain subject field of science and is characteristic of it) competence. Abilities, skills and competences as a component of general (research, teamwork, problem solving, managerial, creativity, communicative skills, information transfer) and professional (occupational, subject) competencies that are clearly relevant to a specific field of scientific knowledge, possibility to demonstrate this knowledge and ability to apply research methods and tools (substantive, normative, legal, organizational, andragogical, constructive, control and evaluation, etc.) are identified and specified.

It is concluded that the concept «integral competence of academic staff for the system of postgraduate education» is understood as the ability to solve difficult specialized complex tasks and professional problems in the field of educational sciences by means of psychological and pedagogical, scientific research, innovative, scientific and methodological, project, managerial, cultural and educational activities in the dynamic conditions of postgraduate, higher education institutions, based on the knowledge of andragogy, synergetics, acmeology, as well as new paradigms of native and foreign science in the field of education that provides deep rethinking of existing and creation of new integrated knowledge and / or professional practice, implementation of innovations and contributes to the qualitative performance of their duties, expanding their competence, etc.

Keywords: *integral competence, general and professional competences, the system of postgraduate pedagogical education*

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ANTHROPOLOGICAL TURN IN PEDAGOGY: A THEORETICAL-METHODOLOGICAL RESEARCH FOR THE GENERAL VALUE OF HUMAN ACTIVITIES

p. 29-37

Inna Dyachenko, PhD, Associate Professor, Department of Natural and Social Sciences and Humanities, Communal Higher Educational Institution «Zhytomyr Medical Institute» Zhytomyr Regional Council, Velyka Berdychivska str., 46/15, Zhytomyr, Ukraine, 10002

E-mail: i-dyachenko@ukr.net

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-9047-671X>

The author of this idea argues that a person has a natural nature, which makes his/her life-supporting potential, which defines a person as a force that generates purposeful actions. An activity that is recognized as an innate potential was inherent in it. The goal is to ensure the greatest possible disclosure of opportunities for cooperation and the creation of conditions for its manifestation. Human is a living being, internally active, self-moving towards the goal: to be alive, to be active. Human must survive to reach his/her limit. The fuller the cognitive potential of a person, the more focused its use will be, the better the life of the person will be. Life exists for the sake of which a human exists. In order for him/her to live, he/she must realize his/her vital potential in its entirety. Value is a form of manifestation of the goal. What goals, such will be the values. The goal is life, the common value is formed in accordance with the goal, there will also be one - the desire / love for life (filomenological). The measure of awareness of the purpose of its existence and human activity, as well as the level of development of common values determines the nature of attitudes towards everything that he / she chooses, how he/she acts and the result of his/her activities. You must say that it was a love of life in general. Human has yet to learn to live among the living. Pedagogy

receives a “foothold”, an invariant that allows it to respond adequately to the anthropological turn, according to which a person lives on the ruins of the old culture, and the new evolution cannot create, optimize the processes of modernization of education, upbringing of modern man and preservation of human society

Keywords: anthropological turn, man, life, living, homo vivens, goal, filomenological, potential

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FEATURES OF PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING OF TEACHERS OF TECHNICAL HIGHER SCHOOLS OF THE USSR IN THE 1940s-60s.

p. 37-42

Galyna Lysenko, PhD, Associate Professor, Department of Ukrainian studies, State Higher Educational Establishment “Prydniprov'ska State Academy of Civil Engineering and Architecture”, Chernyshevskogo str., 24a, Dnipro, Ukraine, 49600

E-mail: galynalysenko@i.ua

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-6216-5025>

The article is devoted to the study of the features of vocational and pedagogical training of teachers for higher technical educational institutions during 1940s–60s. The main objectives of the article are to determine the factors that influenced the development of a higher technical school during the specified period; identification of the main tendencies of the process of providing technical universities with scientific and pedagogical workers; and most importantly – an analysis of the pedagogical component of teaching staff training for higher technical schools of the designated time. The sources of the research were the numerous cases of the funds of the State Archives of the Dnipropetrovsk region (DADO) concerning the post-graduate course of technical universities of Dnipropetrovsk during 1940s–1960s. The results of the study confirmed the widespread thesis about poor provision of the educational process in the high school of the 1940s-60s by curricular staff with academic degrees. It is important to note one more tendency of the development of the high technical school of the UkrSSR during 1940s-1960s - the formation of a hierarchical system of interdependencies between the structural units of a separate institution of higher education and state authorities of different levels. No decision taken in the walls of higher education, did not pass the attention of the ministry or the corresponding agency of the republican, and often even the union level. Such rigorous

subordination of the activity of educational institutions in the field of personnel policy (with the exception of the assignment of the academic title of lecturer) once again proved total control in the Soviet state in all spheres of life, and the field of education and science was no exception. All scientific and scientific-pedagogical workers were subjected to thorough accounting and annual reporting on their activities (as well as nationality, party membership, marital status, etc.). As the process of replenishment of the teaching staff by the new members in general was going very slowly, the pedagogical component of the mentioned process was also organized very formally. The archival sources indicate a lack of attention to the organization of postgraduate pedagogical practice, their participation in the work of the departments, and the involvement of students in scientific and technical circles

Keywords: *technical higher educational establishment, professorial teaching staff, pedagogical practice, post-graduate study*

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BUSINESS GAME AS A METHOD OF INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF FORMING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

p. 43-48

Liudmyla Volkova, PhD, Associate Professor, Department for Modern European Languages, University of State Fiscal Service of Ukraine, Universytetska str., 31, Irpin, Kyiv region, Ukraine, 08201

E-mail: liudavolkova@gmail.com

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-7007-4377>

The article analyzes the main structural elements of the business game for the formation of students' foreign communication skills. The importance of understanding the basic structural elements of the business game for its effective use in the process of learning a foreign language has been proved. For the effective organization of business games in the educational process, the main structural elements are identified. In particular, in the structure of the business game we distinguish: the purpose and objectives of the game; game situation; set of roles; rules of the game. The specificity of the approach to the organization

of educational and cognitive activities of students with the use of business games should ensure the development and improvement of their skills to analyze and investigate professional situations and to choose ways of their solution, to form values and ideals of the individual, to provide their own concept of life and to improve the methods of its practical implementation.

In the process of studying a foreign language, the method of a business game has the aim to teach communication in the solution of professional problems, and its tasks are mastering a set of skills and abilities sufficient and necessary for future speech activity, as well as mastering the linguistic material that ensures the formation and development of a foreign language communicative competence. Game activity is considered as a process of solving a number of professional tasks by students aimed at achieving the overall goal of teaching, educating and developing the student's personality.

It is proved that the main goal of studying a foreign language at the university is to form the foreign language communicative competence of students, which implies the use of language as a means of communication in the field of future professional activities. The process of the business game is aimed on the realization of this purpose.

The solution of the speech tasks creates conditions for the student's communicative practice during the game. Communicative practice involves the development of skills clearly, logically formulate their thoughts, namely: be able to do generalizations on the basis of examples, conduct an analogy, evaluate priorities, find reasons, have a conversation, dialogue, discussion, that is, be able to listen and express the thoughts clearly

Keywords: *business game, structural elements, communicative competence, foreign language communication, speech activity*

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